

Viscosities of 1,2-Dibromoethane + Aromatic Hydrocarbon Mixtures and Prediction of Excess Thermodynamic Functions

K. C. KALRA*, K. C. SINGH and D. C. SPAH

Chemistry Department, Maharshi Dayanand University, Rohtak-124 001

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The viscosity data of binary mixtures of 1,2-dibromoethane (DBE) with benzene, *o*-, *m*- and *p*-xylenes have been experimentally obtained over the whole composition range at 298.15 K and the interactions existing between the components have been discussed. The excess viscosity data have been utilised to evaluate excess volume functions (V^E) and there is a close agreement between the V^E values calculated from the viscosity data and those obtained using a dilatometer. The values of excess Gibbs free energy of flow (G^E) have been calculated from the viscosities of the binary mixtures. η^E , V^E and G^E values show the existence of weak specific interactions of electron donor-acceptor type between the components in which aromatic hydrocarbon behaves as electron donor.

Viscosity data and excess thermodynamic functions of binary mixtures have been used by various workers¹ to know the nature of interactions between their components. Relations between viscosity and excess thermodynamic functions are also known and these functions can be determined from the viscosity data. Our earlier studies of excess volume and excess enthalpies², isentropic compressibilities³, dielectric and spectroscopic studies⁴ of 1,2-dibromoethane + benzene or toluene or *o*-, *m*- and *p*-xylenes have shown the existence of weak specific interactions of electron donor-acceptor type in which the aromatic hydrocarbon behaves as electron donor. Therefore, in the present investigation, the viscosities of binary mixtures of 1,2-dibromoethane with benzene, toluene, *o*-, *m*- and *p*-xylenes have been experimentally measured over the whole composition range at 298.15 K. Viscosity data have been utilised to evaluate excess volume of mixing (V_a^E) and excess Gibb's free energy of flow (G^{E*}).

Results and Discussion

The viscosity data as a function of mole fraction x_1 for DBE (1) + aromatic hydrocarbon (2) mixtures at 298.15 K are reported in Table 1. The excess viscosities (η^E) for these mixtures were calculated using equation (1) and are shown in Fig. 1.

$$\eta^E = \eta_m - [x_1\eta_1 + x_2\eta_2] \quad (1)$$

the η^E data were fitted to equation (2),

$$\eta^E = x_1x_2[A + B(2x_1 - 1) + C(2x_1 - 1)^2] \quad (2)$$

where A , B and C are adjustable parameters. Their values along with standard deviations (σ_{η^E}) are reported in Table 2. The sign of η^E are negative for all the mixtures and the order of variation at equimole fraction is : DBE + *o*-xylene > DBE + *m*-xylene \approx DBE + benzene \approx DBE + toluene > DBE + *p*-xylene. The difference in molecular size

and shape of the components may be one of the reasons for the difference in η^E values. The negative values of η^E in these systems suggest the presence of complex formation. The existence of complex formation has also been revealed by our earlier studies⁴ of excess permittivities, excess refractive indices and nmr spectroscopy of these mixtures. Since the degree of complex formation in these mixtures is of varying strength, this is another factor contributing towards the differences in the η^E values. The curves for all these mixtures show a maximum, indicating the formation of a stable complex between DBE and aromatic hydrocarbon through the transfer of electrons from the π -orbitals of aromatic hydrocarbon to empty $3d$ -orbitals of bromine atom of DBE. Thus η^E values of these mixtures show the existence of weak specific interactions of electron donor/acceptor type between the components in which aromatic hydrocarbon behaves as electron donor.

Grunberg and Nissan⁵ suggested a relation between the viscosity of the mixtures and viscosity of pure components,

$$\ln \eta_m = x_1 \ln \eta_1 + x_2 \ln \eta_2 + x_1x_2d_{12} \quad (3)$$

where d_{12} is a measure of the strength of interaction between the mixing species. The values of d_{12} calculated using equation (3) are reported in Table 1. At equimole fraction, the order of variation of d_{12} , i.e. strength of interactions is DBE + *o*-xylene > DBE + toluene > DBE + benzene; this is as expected since the electron-donating power varies in that order, i.e. *o*-xylene > toluene > benzene. The abnormal behaviour in case of *m*-xylene and *p*-xylene may be due to steric repulsion between the bulky methyl groups. The values of interaction parameter H_{12} were also calculated using the viscosity model proposed by Hind *et al.*⁶,

$$\eta_m = x_1^2\eta_1 + x_2^2\eta_2 + 2x_1x_2H_{12} \quad (4)$$

TABLE 1—EXCESS VISCOSITIES AND CALCULATED EXCESS VOLUME OF MIXING (V^E), EXCESS GIBBS FREE ENERGY OF FLOW (GE^*) AND VARIOUS INTERACTION PARAMETERS OF BINARY MIXTURES OF DBE (1) + AROMATIC HYDROCARBONS (2)

x_1	$\eta_m \times 10^2$ P	$\eta^E \times 10^2$ P	d_{12}	H_{12}	GE^* J mol ⁻¹	V^E cm ³ mol ⁻¹	T_{12}
DBE (1)+Benzene (2) :							
0.051 4	0.627	-0.054	-0.702 7	0.006 9	- 84	0.054 1	0.007 0
0.102 7	0.637	-0.085	-0.745 3	0.006 7	-170	0.085 2	0.006 7
0.153 9	0.656	-0.119	-0.686 9	0.003 6	-221	0.119 3	0.006 8
0.204 9	0.681	-0.146	-0.626 0	0.006 8	-252	0.146 3	0.006 8
0.306 3	0.734	-0.197	-0.596 4	0.006 6	-312	0.197 4	0.006 7
0.407 2	0.812	-0.223	-0.514 5	0.006 7	-307	0.223 5	0.006 8
0.507 5	0.907	-0.231	-0.447 2	0.006 7	-276	0.231 5	0.006 8
0.607 2	0.999	-0.241	-0.473 0	0.006 2	-279	0.241 5	0.006 3
0.804 8	1.231	-0.212	-0.620 7	0.004 6	-241	0.212 4	0.004 7
DBE (1)+Toluene (2) :							
0.060 9	0.587	-0.039	-0.322 8	0.007 6	- 42	0.023 2	0.007 9
0.120 3	0.611	-0.079	-0.399 9	0.007 3	- 99	0.046 9	0.007 6
0.178 5	0.645	-0.108	-0.346 5	0.007 3	-118	0.064 1	0.007 7
0.235 4	0.674	-0.141	-0.378 2	0.007 1	-159	0.083 7	0.007 5
0.345 4	0.742	-0.192	-0.399 6	0.006 8	-212	0.114 0	0.007 2
0.450 8	0.833	-0.215	-0.355 9	0.006 7	-205	0.127 6	0.007 2
0.551 8	0.914	-0.244	-0.420 6	0.006 1	-244	0.144 9	0.006 7
0.648 7	1.011	-0.252	-0.471 6	0.005 5	-254	0.149 6	0.006 3
0.831 2	0.126 7	-0.193	-0.557 2	0.004 1	-186	0.114 6	0.005 2
DBE (1)+ <i>o</i> -Xylene (2) :							
0.068 5	0.777	-0.041	-0.423 2	0.008 8	- 59	0.061 8	0.009 2
0.134 4	0.809	-0.067	-0.324 2	0.009 1	- 78	0.101 0	0.009 6
0.197 8	0.845	-0.087	-0.222 9	0.009 3	- 87	0.131 1	0.009 8
0.258 9	0.881	-0.105	-0.255 0	0.009 3	- 96	0.158 2	0.009 9
0.374 5	0.939	-0.150	-0.319 1	0.008 8	-154	0.226 0	0.009 5
0.482 3	1.018	-0.166	-0.310 4	0.008 7	-157	0.250 2	0.009 5
0.582 8	1.097	-0.176	-0.331 7	0.008 4	-165	0.265 2	0.009 3
0.677 0	1.183	-0.174	-0.357 5	0.008 0	-162	0.262 2	0.009 1
0.848 2	1.387	-0.122	-0.401 9	0.007 3	-109	0.183 8	0.008 7
DBE (1)+ <i>m</i> -Xylene (2) :							
0.070 0	0.620	-0.049	-0.483 9	0.007 4	- 69	0.049 1	0.007 9
0.136 5	0.652	-0.087	-0.412 4	0.007 5	-104	0.087 1	0.008 1
0.200 7	0.686	-0.120	-0.392 0	0.007 5	-133	0.120 2	0.008 1
0.262 4	0.721	-0.150	-0.391 0	0.007 3	-159	0.150 3	0.008 0
0.378 8	0.794	-0.199	-0.413 4	0.007 0	-206	0.199 3	0.007 8
0.486 8	0.877	-0.229	-0.429 8	0.006 6	-228	0.229 4	0.007 6
0.587 3	0.973	-0.238	-0.434 9	0.006 3	-223	0.238 4	0.007 5
0.681 0	1.076	-0.233	-0.459 4	0.005 8	-212	0.233 4	0.007 2
0.850 6	1.315	-0.172	-0.560 2	0.004 4	-155	0.172 3	0.006 3
DBE (1)+ <i>p</i> -Xylene (2) :							
0.070 0	0.629	-0.049	-0.476 7	0.007 5	- 68	0.029 2	0.008 0
0.137 0	0.653	-0.094	-0.511 9	0.007 3	-133	0.056 0	0.007 8
0.201 3	0.687	-0.127	-0.460 3	0.007 3	-160	0.075 6	0.007 9
0.263 0	0.714	-0.162	-0.500 9	0.007 0	-212	0.097 7	0.007 7
0.379 6	0.783	-0.216	-0.515 2	0.006 7	-265	0.128 7	0.007 5
0.487 7	0.861	-0.250	-0.537 8	0.006 2	-294	0.148 9	0.007 0
0.588 1	0.951	-0.264	-0.558 4	0.005 8	-296	0.157 3	0.007 0
0.681 7	1.060	-0.253	-0.554 2	0.554 2	-262	0.150 7	0.006 8
0.851 0	1.304	-0.184	-0.648 5	0.004 0	-182	0.109 6	0.005 9

where H_{12} is the interaction parameter. The values of interaction parameters also indicate similar trends as revealed by Grunberg and Nissan⁶.

Tamura-Kurata relation⁷ for viscosity of binary mixtures is given by equation (5),

$$\eta = x_1 \phi_1 \eta_1 + x_2 \phi_2 \eta_2 + 2(x_1 x_2 \phi_1 \phi_2)^{0.5} T_{12} \quad (5)$$

where T_{12} is the interaction parameter and ϕ_1, ϕ_2 are the volume fractions. The values of T_{12} are found to be concentration-dependent (Table 1). The variation in the order of T_{12} also reflects a pattern similar to the models discussed earlier.

Assuming a three-body interaction model,

McAllister⁸ proposed the following relation for the viscosity of mixtures,

$$\begin{aligned} \ln \eta = & x_1^3 \ln \eta_1 + 3x_1^2 x_2 \ln z_{12} + 3x_1 x_2^2 \ln z_{21} + \\ & x_2^3 \ln \eta_2 - \ln (x_1 + x_2 M_2 / M_1) + 3x_1^2 x_2 \\ & \ln [(2 + M_2 / M_1) / 3] + 3x_1 x_2^2 \ln [(1 + \\ & 2M_2 / M_1) / 3] + x_2 \ln (M_2 / M_1) \end{aligned} \quad (6)$$

where z_{12} and z_{21} are the interaction parameters and M_1 and M_2 the molecular weights of components 1 and 2 respectively. The values of z_{12} and z_{21} were calculated in the volume fraction range 0.4–0.6 of DBE and are reported in Table 3.

Fig. 1. Excess viscosities of mixing of 1,2-dibromoethane (1): (O)+benzene (2), (●)+toluene (2), (□) *o*-xylene (2), (Δ)+*m*-xylene (2) and (×) *p*-xylene (2) at 298.15 K.

The order of variation of interaction parameter z_{21} is DBE + benzene < DBE + toluene < DBE + *o*-xylene \approx DBE + *m*-xylene \approx DBE + *p*-xylene, while that of z_{12} is exactly the reverse. This is expected as the electron-donating power also changes in that order. The values of z_{12} or z_{21} again confirm our earlier contention that the strength of interactions increases as DBE + xylenes > DBE + toluene > DBE + benzene.

TABLE 2—VALUES OF THE PARAMETERS AND STANDARD DEVIATIONS $\sigma(\eta^E)$ FOR 1,2-DIBROMOETHANE (1) AND AROMATIC HYDROCARBON (2) MIXTURES AT 298.15 K

Systems 1,2-Dibromoethane+	$\times 10^3$			$\sigma(\eta^E)$ P
	A	B	C	
Benzene	-0.936	-0.348	-0.520	0.007
Toluene	-0.946	-0.475	-0.239	0.005
<i>o</i> -Xylene	-0.664	-0.269	-0.226	0.005
<i>m</i> -Xylene	-0.912	-0.421	-0.268	0.004
<i>p</i> -Xylene	-0.912	-0.421	-0.268	0.019

Heric and Brewer⁹ proposed an equation for the kinematic viscosity ($\lambda = \eta/\rho$) of binary mixtures, according to which λ is given by

$$\lambda = x_1\lambda_1 + x_2\lambda_2 + x_1x_2[a + b(x_1 - x_2) + c(x_1 - x_2)^2] \quad (7)$$

where λ_1 and λ_2 are kinematic viscosities of components 1 and 2 respectively. We fitted our viscosity data at volume fractions 0.4, 0.5 and 0.6 to equation (7) and the constants a, b, c were evaluated (Table 3). The gradation in the values of constant a shows a trend similar to other models, however, constants b and c do not show any regular gradation.

Recently Singh¹⁰ suggested a relation between excess viscosity (η^E) and excess volume of mixing (V^E),

$$\eta^E = KV^E \quad (8)$$

TABLE 3—VALUES OF McALLISTER CONSTANTS (z_{12} AND z_{21}) AND HERIC AND BREWER CONSTANTS (a, b, c) FOR DIFFERENT BINARY MIXTURES

System	z_{12}	z_{21}	a	b	c
DBE+					
Benzene	1.319 1	45.156 6	-0.005 4	0.001 2	-0.007 6
Toluene	4.653 2	12.320 0	-0.004 1	-0.001 9	0.009 1
<i>o</i> -Xylene	8.688 8	4.674 9	-0.003 2	-0.000 2	-0.000 8
<i>m</i> -Xylene	9.065 6	4.772 6	-0.003 6	0.000 2	-0.002 0
<i>p</i> -Xylene	9.271 9	4.622 0	-0.004 3	-0.000 8	0.001 6

The values of K for these mixtures were evaluated using the experimental values of η^E and V^E (from literature) at $x_1=0.5$ (equimole fraction). The values of K for DBE + benzene, DBE + toluene, DBE + *o*-xylene, DBE + *m*-xylene and DBE + *p*-xylene are found to be -0.9979, -1.6845, -0.6636, -0.9983 and -1.6780 $\text{g cm}^2 \text{s}^{-1} \text{mol}$ respectively. From the experimental η^E data, the V^E values at various mole fractions were calculated (Table 1). The positive sign of V^E also indicates a complex formation between DBE and aromatic hydrocarbon molecules. The V^E values calculated from viscosity data using equation (8) are compared with our earlier reported V^E values⁸ obtained dilatometrically in Fig. 2. The agreement between the V^E values obtained by the two methods is reasonably good.

The excess Gibbs free energy of flow (G^{E*}) is given by Eyring's relation¹¹,

$$G^{E*} = RT \left[\ln \eta_m V - \sum_i x_i \ln \eta_i V_i \right] \quad (9)$$

where V_i is molar volume of i -th component and R and T have usual meaning. The values of G^{E*}

Fig. 2. Comparison of V^E values (---) calculated from the viscosity data with that (—) obtained dilatometrically: (I) benzene+1,2-DBE and (II) toluene+1,2-DBE.

calculated using viscosity data from equation (9) are reported in Table 1. The negative values of G^{E*} also suggest complex formation between DBE

and aromatic hydrocarbons and the magnitudes of values of G^E reveal the same order of strength of interactions.

Experimental

1,2-Dibromoethane (DBE), benzene, toluene, *o*-xylene, *m*-xylene, and *p*-xylene (all AnalaR) were purified by standard procedures¹². Their purity was checked by density determination (dilatometrically) at 298.15 ± 0.01 K, which agreed to within $\pm 5 \times 10^{-5}$ g cm⁻³ with the available literature values¹³. Viscosities accurate to $\pm 1 \times 10^{-5}$ poise of binary mixtures were determined using an Ubbelohde viscometer which was suspended in a water-bath maintained at 298.15 ± 0.01 K. The viscosity of the mixture (ρ_m) was calculated from the relation,

$$\eta_m^r = \eta_w \frac{\rho_m}{\rho_w} \times \frac{t_m^r}{t_w^r} \quad (10)$$

where η_w is the coefficient of viscosity of water, ρ_m and ρ_w are densities and t_m and t_w the time of flow for the mixture and water respectively. The values of ρ_m were also measured dilatometrically. For this, initially V^E values were calculated and therefrom the ρ_m values were evaluated using the well-known relation,

$$V^E = x_1 M_1 [\rho_m^{-1} \rho_1^{-1}] + x_2 M_2 [\rho_m^{-1} - \rho_2^{-1}] \quad (11)$$

where x and M are mole fraction and molecular mass and suffixes 1 and 2 represent components 1 and 2 respectively.

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